

Resource constraint federated learning for Energy Smart Meters

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This dissertation is submitted in partial fulfillment for the degree of
MSc in Electronic Information Engineering

I would like to dedicate this thesis to my sister and my loving parents ...

Declaration

I declare that this thesis has not been submitted as an exercise for a degree at this or any other university and it is entirely my own work. It contains nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

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Abhishek Duttagupta
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Abstract

The project focuses on simulating a Federated Learning framework using the London Household smart energy meter dataset. The primary objective is to achieve comparable accuracy in load forecasting to state-of-the-art (SOTA) technologies while demonstrating the preservation of data privacy through FL. In real-world scenarios, the challenge of non-i.i.d. connections persists. To replicate real-world conditions, limited random connections are considered for each round of FL. Additionally, since smart meters often have limited computational power, small sequential dense neural networks (DNN) are utilized to address this constraint. These DNN models are well-suited for low computational power devices and contribute to solving the computational challenges posed by smart meters. Through this project, the aim is to showcase the potential of FL in maintaining data privacy while achieving accurate load forecasting results, even in resource-constrained environments.

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Nomenclature

Acronyms / Abbreviations

AI Artificial Intelligence

ARIMA Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average

CNN Convolutional Neural Network

DL Deep Learning

DNN Deep Neural Nets

FL Federated Learning

GDPR General Data Protection Regulation

GRU Gated Recurrent Unit

i.i.d Independent and Identically Distributed

IoT Internet-of-Things

LSTM Long Short Term Memory

MAE Mean Absolute Error

MAPE Mean Absolute Percentage Error

ML Machine Learning

RMSE Root Mean Squared Error

SOTA State-of-the-art

TFF TensorFlow Federated

TF TensorFlow

CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1.1 Overview

"A Federated learning approach towards the smart energy meter dataset" provides a simulated demonstration of how federated learning (FL) [2, 3] can effectively address the privacy concerns [4] associated with traditional load forecasting machine learning techniques[5]. The project showcases nearly comparable accuracies to those achieved by conventional methods while utilizing small Deep neural network (DNN) models [6]. The results obtained through this approach are analyzed in detail, focusing on the algorithm's performance. In summary, the project highlights the potential of federated learning to mitigate privacy concerns, in load forecasting, while maintaining accuracy levels.

This section serves as an introduction to the problem at hand and provides a short overview of the motivation involved in this project. The incitement behind the project is described in a chronological sequence of questionnaires in a "what," "why," and "where" format for better understanding.

1.2 What is machine learning in a centralized context and how it is harmful?

Centralized techniques for machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) [6] have been extensively employed in various domains, including text generation, image classification, stock forecasting, and data analysis. However, with each groundbreaking advancement in this field, the process becomes progressively more data-intensive. The fundamental empirical rule employed in this procedure involves collecting data from one or multiple sources, storing it on a centralized server for training purposes, and utilizing this training evaluation to predict future outcomes. Nonetheless, acquiring a sufficient amount of data is increasingly challenging, and the issue of privacy [4] has arisen with the use of these techniques. As artificial intelligence (AI) applications increasingly rely on personal, commercial, scientific, or ethically sensitive data, ensuring compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) regulations becomes crucial. A mere breach or leakage [7] of this personal data can divulge sensitive information about the nature of the utilized data. Consequently, a significant ethical question emerges: How can data be effectively safeguarded to protect individuals' privacy and maintain ethical standards?

1.3 What is Federated learning and how does it solve the problem?

Federated learning (FL) [2, 3] is a unique type of ML algorithm that facilitates the training of data at the edge 1.1. By enabling data training at the edge, only the model parameters or updates are shared with the centrally located server [8]. With diverse model updates originating from various sources, these updates are aggregated to create a single global model. This global model is then shared back to edge devices to undergo further training and send back updates, thereby continuing the cycle [9]. The key advantage of this entire process is that the data remains solely at the edges, with only the model parameters being shared. Consequently, FL overcomes the privacy concerns associated with centralized ML techniques [10, 11].

The image below 1.1, describes the general working phenomenon behind an FL setup, with edge devices and server. The process is described in detail in Chapter 2.

Figure 1: Federated Learning Protocol

Fig. 1.1 Federated Learning Protocol as explained in Bonawitz's paper. [1].

1.4 What is Load Forecasting and how do smart energy meters aid in this process?

Electricity demand forecasting [5] is an indispensable function within the energy production industry and utility boards, aimed at achieving a balanced supply and demand curve while maintaining a stable load on the energy grid. Behind the intricacies of load forecasting, smart energy meters [12] play a vital role. In addition to integrating various Internet of Things (IoT) devices [13] and monitoring load, they enable the transmission of demand data to central electricity boards. By leveraging a wealth of data from diverse locations, these boards can train their models to predict future load curves. This information, in turn, allows them to announce dynamic pricing tariff rates [14] that help achieve supply-demand equilibrium.

While Load Forecasting can be divided broadly into long-term, mid-term, and short-term time forecasting. Our approach deals with short-term forecasting, predicting forecasts on a half-hourly basis using smart meter data in a federated way.

Fig. 1.2 Traditional Centralized Setup for Load Forecasting.

Fig. 1.3 Federated Learning Setup for Load Forecasting.

1.5 What is wrong with the traditional methods used in load forecasting?

With centralized training still being performed for load forecasting, the issue of privacy concerns arises. As shown in 1.2, where in centralized all data from individual houses smart meters go to a central server at substation level for model training for load forecasting, a single breach or hack exposing a customer's smart meter data is sufficient to discern the nature of that customer [15]. What is even more concerning is that, based on a customer's electricity usage profile, one can easily deduce their home occupancy pattern and the specific types of equipment they use [16]. Therefore, it is crucial and imperative to address these privacy concerns. To prevent such incidents, privacy-preserving ML techniques, such as FL, should be employed while ensuring the continuity of the load forecasting process. By leveraging FL, as shown in 1.3, data from an individual house's smart meter can be kept secure and private, allowing the collaborative training of models without the need to share sensitive information centrally. This approach ensures the protection of customer privacy while still achieving accurate load forecasting results.

1.6 Where has federated learning been used before in such a context?

While FL has a lot of applications already for mobile devices, recently there has been a rise in publications of papers calling for its use in industrial and medical applications. Below are a few cases that can be studied for a better understanding of federated learning scope in industrial and medical applications.

1. Taking environmental protection as a case point, Hu, Gao, Liu, and Ma (2018) [17] came up with a novel environmental monitoring frame based on federated region learning against the problem of inconvenient interchangeable monitor data. Thus, monitoring data taken from various sensors could be employed and utilized for higher performance of the collaborative model.
2. Upon popularization of EVs, Saputra et al. (2019) [18] sketched a federated energy demand prediction process for charging stations across to stop energy congestion in the transmission process.
3. Similarly, Electronic health records (EMR) consist of a lot of meaningful clinical data. Pfohl, Dai, and Heller (2019) [19] investigated differentially private learning

for EMR in a federated setting. And they further concluded that the performance is comparable with training in a centralized setting.

4. With the utilization of health records, Lee et al. (2018) [20] demonstrated a federated patient hashing framework which detects similar patients located in different hospitals without sharing and disclosing patient-level information, helping doctors to summarize general character and lead them to treat patients with more experience.

For further information on various detailed applications and exploration on the use of FL in different fields refer to. [21]

1.7 What are the general problems associated with Federated learning?

While the use of FL appears to be the way forward for various ML applications, it presents its own unique set of challenges. One such challenge is the requirement for strong computational devices at the edge [22] for data training. While certain devices like mobile phones possess decent computational power, IoT devices, and smart energy meters, along with similar electronic data-facilitating hardware, may lack such capabilities [23]. Additionally, the problem of non-i.i.d. [24, 25] connectivity between the edge and server arises, as not all edge devices are available simultaneously for model updates. This can impact the overall performance of the global model. Extensive research is still being conducted to address these challenges and ensure that FL matches the accuracy and performance of centralized frameworks.

Despite these challenges, the trade-off provided by data privacy in FL offers a significant boost to its adoption. The ongoing efforts to overcome the technical hurdles in federated learning demonstrate its potential to revolutionize the field while upholding data privacy standards.

1.8 How are these problems tackled in this project and What novelty is shown in this work?

This project focuses on simulating an FL framework using the London Household smart energy meter dataset. The primary objective is to achieve comparable accuracy in load forecasting to state-of-the-art (SOTA) technologies while demonstrating the preservation of data privacy through FL. In real-world scenarios, the challenge of non-i.i.d. connections

1.8 How are these problems tackled in this project and What novelty is shown in this work?

persists, which means a scenario, even though we have 100 clients available for the global server, only half of them are ready to connect based on the network connectivity. To replicate real-world conditions, limited random connections are considered for each round of FL. Additionally, since smart meters often have limited computational power, small sequential dense neural networks (DNN) are utilized to address this constraint. For our case, we define small as DL models which have a very less number of parameters. These DNN models are well-suited for low computational power devices and contribute to solving the computational challenges posed by smart meters. Through this project, the aim is to showcase the potential of FL in maintaining data privacy while achieving accurate load forecasting results, even in resource-constrained environments.

CHAPTER 2

Literature Review, Related Works and Concepts

2.1 A brief history on load forecasting

With the advent and success of ML and the beginning of the use of smart grids, various algorithms have been adapted for load forecasting for dynamic energy pricing, helping consumers to plan their usage and costs accordingly. Moreover, similar algorithms have been tried and tested for other activities like prediction grid maintenance schedules, and customers integrating renewable energy sources to the grid with these dynamic pricing predictions.

While many models have been developed for forecasting peak electric load, there are limited publications for this forecast on the use of the billing period. Guzman Diaz [14] used a model of gradient-boosted regression trees on the Spanish Energy data set for a day-ahead forecast and concluded a very minimum prediction error. This paved the way for advanced algorithms and ML for bringing models with better accuracy.

Load forecasting is a difficult task owing to the stochastic nature of the different customer usage profiles. The inclusion of spatial-temporal parameters in load forecasting had a major impact on load prediction, demonstrated by A. Tascikaraoglu [26]. The impact of area-based clustering for grouping similar spatiotemporal customers was likewise a major predicament in the load forecasting story, demonstrated by K. Bandara [27] and F. L. Quilumba [28].

A major breakthrough was obtained by, Saxena and his colleagues [29] who developed a hybrid model, which forecasted whether a day would be a peak load day or not, predicting

70 percent of the actual peak days. The model used comprised ARIMA, logistic regressions, and DNNs. Similarly, Andreas Ikonmopoulou [30] and Sadaei [31] proposed a similar approach but with a different model made of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) based on fuzzy time series, achieving superior results than traditionally used state of art models. Standalone LSTM model by Memarzadeh G. [32], LSTM combined CNN model from Guo.X [33] and GRU combined CNN model from Sajjad. M [34] showed similar prediction performance.

Further, a model made from Rolling updates and Bi-LSTMs [35] was proposed and directly tested on Australian Energy Data sets, significantly improving predictions with less computational time.

2.2 Federated Learning approach on Load forecasting

While there are very limited works of federated learning in the application of load forecasting. The below two works stand out from the rest.

1. Nastaran [36] proposed an FL-based LSTM + DNN approach for training models in a distributed, collaborative manner whilst retaining the privacy of the data. Moreover, he used a clustering method to narrow down similar clients in the same clusters and then concluded that by clustering, the model performance improved a lot, benchmarking it with Root mean squared error (RMSE) Values. However, the back-drop remained, despite using complex LSTM combined DNN models, the federated RMSE was not as good as the centralized model-based RMSE demonstrated in the paper.
2. M Savi's paper proposes [37] a global generalized model which is aggregated from many Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models which are locally trained by different users based on their own past energy consumption data. This model is then re-distributed for improved prediction at the edge. Though accuracy and error take up a hit when samples are recorded at an interval of more than one hour, Nevertheless, it keeps sensitive data local and hence guarantees users' privacy. This approach also takes spatiotemporal factors for the clustering approach and RMSE Values are for comparing results, which shows better results compared to Nastaran's [36] work.

While all the federated works implemented so far in load forecasting have employed complex models to get a proper prediction, our work aims to obtain a similar prediction but by only using small DNNs. This approach makes it more realistic, in regards to smart

meters not having enough computational prowess to undergo edge training with complex models.

Further, in our prediction calculation, the temporal aspect is not considered, due to the fact and study shown in Savi's work [37], where he computed the importance of different features used, with respect to the accuracy of prediction. This study showed that only energy consumption played a vital role, in prediction, with other factors like temperature having very little impact. Nevertheless, this may vary from region to region and might be applicable and important to different datasets. The below table 2.1 summarizes the above two works in comparison to this proposed simulation.

Table 2.1 Comparison of works where FL is used for load forecasting

Author	Model	Evaluation Metrics
M. Savi	Clustering + LSTM	RMSE
Nastaran	Clustering + LSTM	RMSE
A. Taik	LSTM	RMSE, MAPE
Our Work	Clustering + DNN	RMSE, MAPE

2.3 Important Federated Learning and Neural Network Terminologies

Here, we define some terminologies that will be used throughout the thesis.

2.3.1 Batch Size

Batch size refers to the number of samples that are propagated through the neural network in one forward and backward pass (iteration) during training. Instead of updating the weights for each individual sample, the model's weights are updated based on the average gradient computed from a batch of samples. For our case, we choose between batch sizes 12, 24, or 48, as here the sizes mean a half-day equivalent or full-day equivalent data as batch size.

2.3.2 Learning Rate

The learning rate is a hyper-parameter that determines the step size at which the model's weights are updated during training. It controls the speed and magnitude of weight updates in the optimization process. The lower the learning rate, the slower the will be

convergence time, but there will be more chances of convergence. For our case, we select between 0.02 and 0.01 as our learning rate on the client side and 1 on the global model side. This is because, at the global server side, the task is only unweighted averaging for our case, and having a learning rate of 1, is ideal for this.

2.3.3 Epoch

Epoch means the number of times the local model will iterate over the entire client training dataset. During each epoch, the model is exposed to each sample in the training dataset once. Increasing the number of epochs can lead to better convergence, but it is necessary to reach an optimal balance between convergence and avoiding over-fitting.

2.3.4 Shuffle Buffer

The shuffle buffer is used to shuffle the data during training. It is a buffer that stores a certain number of samples, and during each epoch, the training dataset is randomly shuffled within this buffer. This helps introduce randomness into the training process, which can prevent the model from memorizing the order of the data and improve generalization. For our context, we keep a shuffling buffer, so that when the local model is transferred to the global server, a little more randomization might improve the privacy.

2.3.5 Federated Averaging

Federated Averaging is one of the methods of global aggregation used to create the global model in the central server, based on the local model updates. In our case, by federated averaging, we mean taking the unweighted average of the local weights to obtain the global weights. This approach allows each client in the federated learning system to independently train its local model on its own data, and then the central server aggregates the model updates by averaging their weights without assigning any specific weights or importance to each client's update. This way, all clients contribute equally to the formation of the global model.

2.3.6 Federated Rounds

In federated learning, the term "federated rounds" is synonymous with "epoch" in centralized training, but with a slightly different interpretation. Instead of processing the entire training dataset in one central location, federated rounds refer to the number of times the global server receives updates from the local edge devices (clients). In each federated

round, the server aggregates the model updates received from the participating clients and updates the global model accordingly.

2.4 The Federated Learning approach explained

2.4.1 General Algorithm

Fig. 2.1 Federated Learning Flow Diagram.

While the complete structure of a federated algorithm flow is explained in detail by Bonawitz [9, 1], a similar and simpler flowchart 2.1 and algorithm 1 simplified from Macmahan's implementation [3] has been used for this purpose.

In the initial step, a set of user devices ($N=0,1,2,\dots,n$) are selected from the total device set (M), where an initial global model (W) is initialized and passed to these devices. Then training is performed on these selected devices in parallel using the local data (P) on each device, keeping the sizes of batches (B), learning rate (η), and local epochs (E) in mind. After

the training, the updated model of these devices(w) is shared with the substation where presumably the central server is, where federated averaging occurs for server aggregation for these models, based on which a global Model is created(W). Once a global model is created, it is again shared with all the devices, which then updates its model, and the same process is repeated.

Algorithm 1 Federated Learning Algorithm

Require: Total device set M , selected device set N , batch size B , learning rate η , local epochs E

Ensure: Global model W

- 1: Initialization: Randomly initialize global model W
 - 2: **while** not converged **do**
 - 3: **for** each device n in selected device set N **do**
 - 4: Retrieve local data P on device n
 - 5: Train local model w_n on data P for E epochs with batch size B and learning rate η
 - 6: Share local model w_n with central server
 - 7: **end for**
 - 8: Aggregate models w_n from all devices on a central server using federated averaging
 - 9: Update global model W as the average of all local models w_k
 - 10: Share global model W with all devices
 - 11: **end while**
-

2.4.2 The Maths explained

As explained in Zebang Shen's paper [38], considering a situation where we have an FL setup with n clients communicating with the global server(substation for our case), assuming each client has a k fixed number of data points in its respective dataset, through 2.1, we can represent the input and output function for a given local dataset S for a client i . Here x and y represent the input and output vectors.

$$\mathcal{S}_i = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^{k_i} \quad (2.1)$$

Let us consider a model $f(\cdot; \theta)$, which maps an input x to the predicted label y . Here θ is the trainable parameter of the model f . Let L be a loss function for this model for the error of the prediction $f(x; \theta)$ given the true label y .

Based on this, we can define the local objective of the client i through 2.2 and the global server objective through 2.3.

$$L(\theta; \mathcal{S}_i) = \frac{1}{k_i} \sum_{i=1}^{k_i} l(f(x_i; \theta), y_i) \quad (2.2)$$

$$\arg \min_{\theta} L(\theta) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n L(\theta; \mathcal{S}_i) \quad (2.3)$$

2.5 Performance Metrics

In the context of load forecastings, metrics such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE) 2.4 and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) 2.5 are commonly used to compute the loss between the actual and predicted values. However, when dealing with half-hourly energy consumption in small units like kWh, MAE alone may not provide a comprehensive assessment of the prediction accuracy.

Due to the small magnitude of energy consumption values, a large MAE might not accurately reflect the quality of the prediction. Therefore, in such cases, it is preferred to primarily use RMSE and MAPE for evaluation purposes. RMSE provides a more reliable estimate of the prediction performance, as it considers the squared differences between the actual and predicted values, effectively taking into account the magnitude of the errors and MAPE, 2.6 shows the percentage of the percentage deviation obtained in predicted values from the actual values. While both MAE and RMSE might depend on a household average consumption, MAPE is a metric that can be used independently across any kind of household. So overall using MAE, RMSE, and MAPE all together, gets a clear picture of our prediction accuracy.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |X(i) - Y(i)| \quad (2.4)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N [X(i) - Y(i)]^2} \quad (2.5)$$

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left| \frac{X(i) - Y(i)}{X(i)} \right| \times 100 \quad (2.6)$$

For all the above equations, X represents the actual value and Y represents the predicted value, with N as the number of data points.

CHAPTER 3

Overall Architecture

Here, through a few flowcharts, we demonstrate what the architecture of our complete simulation looks like, with a detailed section explanation in the next chapters.

3.1 Top To Cluster Level Architecture

The first flowchart 3.1 glances at the initial steps that were performed before entering the clustering-wise operation. This mainly involved pre-processing of the data and K-Means to split the data into different data groups.

3.2 Cluster Level Architecture

The Cluster level architecture 3.2 contains the creation of federated datasets, showing the federation round cycles and testing process. A detailed explanation of the complete process is provided in Chapter 4.

Fig. 3.1 Top to Cluster level Simulation Architecture

Fig. 3.2 Cluster level Simulation Architecture

CHAPTER 4

Methodology and Simulation

4.1 System Specifications

The whole project was conducted in a system using 12th Generation Intel i7-12700K, 3.6 GHz, in Google Collab-based Jupyter Notebook mainly using the TensorFlow federated and TensorFlow libraries in the back end.

4.2 Data Pre-Processing

The pre-processing stage involves conducting a detailed analysis of the selected dataset, examining it closely to identify any outliers that could potentially impact the forecasting process, and subsequently eliminating those outliers.

4.2.1 Dataset Selection

For our simulation and testing, we selected the smart meter energy consumption dataset from London Households. This dataset comprises energy consumption data recorded from smart meters installed in 5,567 households across London. The data covers the period from November 2011 to February 2014, with half-hour energy consumption data.

These 5,567 households can be categorized into two groups. The first group consists of 1,100 households that were subjected to a dynamic time of usage charge. This charge was determined based on a one-day forecast received the day before. The second group

comprises the remaining 4,567 households, which were billed at standard tariff rates according to their consumption usage.

Upon initial examination of the dataset 4.1, we observe that it consists of four columns.

- The first column is labeled "LCLid," which corresponds to the customer or household tag number.
- The second column is named "StdorTou" and indicates the type of household, distinguishing between standard and dynamic categories.
- The third column, labeled "Datetime," provides the timestamps for the data, recorded on a half-hourly basis
- Lastly, the fourth column is titled "Kwh/hh" and represents the energy consumption values in kilowatt-hours per half-hourly intervals.

	LCLid	stdorTou	DateTime	KWH/hh
0	MAC000002	Std	2012-10-12 00:30:00.0000000	0
1	MAC000002	Std	2012-10-12 01:00:00.0000000	0
2	MAC000002	Std	2012-10-12 01:30:00.0000000	0
3	MAC000002	Std	2012-10-12 02:00:00.0000000	0
4	MAC000002	Std	2012-10-12 02:30:00.0000000	0
...
167932469	MAC005565	ToU	2012-06-21 05:30:00.0000000	1.022
167932470	MAC005565	ToU	2012-06-21 06:00:00.0000000	0.188
167932471	MAC005565	ToU	2012-06-21 06:30:00.0000000	0.073
167932472	MAC005565	ToU	2012-06-21 07:00:00.0000000	0.025
167932473	MAC005565	ToU	2012-12-19 12:32:41.0000000	Null
167932474 rows × 4 columns				

Fig. 4.1 A glance at the Smart Meter London Household dataset

Before going further into the analysis, it is crucial to examine the heterogeneity of the data and understand how a consumer's energy consumption graph varies daily, weekly,

and yearly. Looking into the daily energy consumption graphs will provide insights into the consumption patterns in a typical day, especially identifying the peak and off-peak periods. In the same manner, analyzing the data on a weekly basis will reveal any recurring patterns that may occur within a week, mostly observing consumption differences on weekdays and weekends. Lastly, understanding energy consumption on a yearly basis will uncover any seasonal variations or long-term trends in consumption.

Below graphs 4.2 shows how regular standard usage and regular dynamic usage consumer data vary throughout a day, a week, and a year. Based on this, we can infer the following points.

- The first graph 4.6a shows how a regular standard and dynamic usage consumer varies in a single day, with the trend showing evenings and nights as peak consumption timings.
- The second graph 4.6b shows the weekly variation of a randomly picked consumer in the month of December. Weekends having more consumption than weekdays is evident from the graph.
- The Third graph 4.2c shows yearly total consumption trend for a random household. On average, January, February, and December months end up having more consumption compared to other months.

Further, in the below graph 4.3, we see the monthly consumption of two consumers having high consumption and one with a medium consumption profile. This shows how varied and heterogeneous the data is in the dataset.

4.2.2 Removing Outliers

In the case of energy consumption data, outliers refer to data points, either individual or grouped, that deviate significantly from the expected consumption trend. The presence of outliers can introduce bias in forecasts or predictions, making it crucial to remove them from the dataset.

To initiate the outlier removal process, we start by eliminating any NaN (Not a Number) or null data points. These missing values are not suitable for analysis and can hinder accurate forecasting.

Next, to identify outliers, we calculate the average consumption for each household in the dataset. By examining the graph 4.4 below, which represents the average consumption of nearly all households, we can visually assess the average values. Based on this analysis

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4.2 Energy Profile (Daily, Weekly, and Yearly)

Fig. 4.3 Energy Consumption Comparison between different type of households

and observing other household averages, we establish a boundary to identify outliers. Specifically, households with an average energy consumption per half-hourly interval less than 0.09 kWh/hh or greater than 1.35 kWh/hh are considered outliers.

By implementing this methodology, we can effectively identify and remove outliers from the dataset, ensuring a more accurate and unbiased forecasting process. Moreover, it becomes a significant step in cleaning the data as we are able to reduce the total number of households from 5567 to 4672.

Fig. 4.4 Mean Energy Consumption (Kwh/hh) across all households

4.3 Clustering

Indeed, clustering plays a significant role in improving predictions, especially in scenarios where federated models are employed. The idea behind clustering is to group similar households together, as this enhances the accuracy of predictions. When applying federated prediction, it becomes even more advantageous to have the global model aggregated with local models that are similar in nature. This ensures that the global model is not biased and benefits from the knowledge and patterns learned from similar households.

On the other hand, using dissimilar local models for global aggregation can introduce biases into the overall predictions. In such cases, the diverse models may not capture the nuances and specific patterns of the target population accurately, leading to less reliable forecasts. Therefore, incorporating clustering before the application of federated prediction makes practical sense.

How many Clusters ?

As explained in M Savi's work [37], the UK Power Networks dataset provides traces' clustering according to customers' behavioral and socioeconomic aspects (ACORN). ACORN classifies residential areas into 18 different categories based on a range of demographic, socioeconomic, and behavioral factors, helping organizations understand the characteristics and preferences of households in different neighborhoods. ACORN takes into account variables such as income, education, housing type, employment, and lifestyle choices to create a detailed segmentation of households.

Based on this, we decided to proceed with clustering the data into **18 groups**, to have traceability. However, since it is a simulation with the Federated Learning application being the bigger goal, the number of exact household traces provided through ACORN is not tallied in our work.

4.3.1 K - Means

A K - Means clustering [39], was performed on the data, clustering it into a further 18 subgroups of data.

The following input parameters as derived from Savi's work, per household, were provided as input to the K-Means Algorithm.

- Mean Energy Consumption
- Median Energy Consumption
- Total Energy Consumption
- Maximum recorded Energy Consumption
- Minimum recorded Energy Consumption

Based on these parameters, each household now falls into a cluster, with cluster No. added to the data frame 4.5.

	LCLid	median_consumption	average_consumption	sum_consumption	highest_consumption	lowest_consumption	cluster
0	MAC000002	0.158	0.252562	6101.138184	2.994	0.000	12
1	MAC000003	0.166	0.397666	14104.432617	3.921	0.007	13
2	MAC000005	0.041	0.095388	2911.808105	1.979	0.010	8
3	MAC000007	0.115	0.197805	4954.017090	3.784	0.015	9
4	MAC000008	0.296	0.363102	9445.006836	3.581	0.000	13
...
4667	MAC005561	0.094	0.152001	4193.401855	1.886	0.017	8
4668	MAC005562	0.170	0.218019	6910.988770	1.879	0.008	16
4669	MAC005565	0.114	0.131591	5.790000	1.022	0.010	11
4670	MAC005566	0.163	0.363100	8946.789062	3.936	0.034	0
4671	MAC005567	0.062	0.108561	2268.485107	1.528	0.027	11

4672 rows × 7 columns

Fig. 4.5 Dataframe with Cluster No included as obtained from k-Means

Looking into the below graph 4.6 and 4.7, we can infer Clusters - 02, 07, and 18 as clusters with higher consumption usage consumers, whereas Clusters - 9 and 12 as the lower consumption usage consumers.

4.4 Creating the Federated Environment

After analyzing and dividing the data into 18 clusters, the aim is to have an optimal global model for each cluster. The objective is to generate load forecasting predictions and evaluate the results based on this approach to assert the effectiveness of our method.

4.4.1 TensorFlow Federated

The whole simulation is done using TensorFlow federated framework, which is an open-source framework by TensorFlow for decentralized machine learning and computations. For applying TensorFlow Federated(TFF), it is imperative to convert our training data into an acceptable form, on which TFF computations can be done. The below flowchart shows the customized process, that was done to create the Federated training and testing data, with details explained in respective sections below.

4.4.2 Federated Training and Testing Data sets Creation

Training and Testing Scenarios

The entire dataset, organized by client tags, was initially partitioned into training and test data. Two distinct conditions were taken into account for this division.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4.6 Scatter and Box Plots showing Cluster wise data distribution - Mean, Median and Total Consumption

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4.7 Box Plots showing Cluster-wise data distribution - Highest and Lowest Recorded Consumption

Fig. 4.8 Flow Diagram for creating Federated Datasets for TFF Implementation

In the first scenario, the training data consisted of the complete data for the year 2012 for each client. This means that all energy consumption records from January to December 2012 were utilized for training. Subsequently, the testing data comprised the energy consumption records for the year 2013, covering the period from January to December.

In the second scenario, both the 2012 and 2013 data were combined to form the training data. Thus, the training data contained the energy consumption records for two consecutive years. The test data, on the other hand, encompassed a two-month duration in 2014.

By splitting the data in these different ways, we can assess the performance and generalization ability of the models when trained on varying time periods and tested on different time ranges. This enables us to evaluate the model's effectiveness in capturing consumption patterns and making accurate predictions for both short-term and long-term time frames.

Input Window and Output Prediction

In the context of load forecasting, a time series problem, it is essential to implement a sliding window algorithm. This algorithm involves transforming the input data into a sliding window format, where the input is represented as an array with a specified window size, and the corresponding output is the predicted value.

In our case, we have chosen 336 as the window size for the sliding window approach. With this, we have been able to encompass a whole week of data. By considering a longer time span that includes weekdays and weekends, we can observe the trends and patterns that emerge throughout a complete week.

Examining the aforementioned demonstration, we can comprehend that for a window size of 336, the input consists of the first 336 data values, while the 337th value serves as the corresponding output. Subsequently, the sliding window shifts by one data point, and the next input array comprises the 2nd to 337th values, with the 338th value serving as the output. This process continues iteratively until the end of the dataset is reached, effectively creating a series of input arrays and their corresponding output data.

TFF Wrapping

TFF wrapping refers to the process of preparing the dataset to be converted into federated data. After applying the sliding window approach and obtaining the input and output

Fig. 4.9 Sliding Window approach for load forecasting approach

data, the entire dataset needs to be transformed into a Python-ordered dictionary, keyed by the household tags. 4.10 shows how an ordered dictionary looks for a random client.

Once we have the Ordered Dictionary representation, TFF wrapping can be applied to the data. For TFF Wrapping, we convert each data type into a tensor object, which is the fundamental required data type for TensorFlow. This enables the conversion of data into a federated dataset, where each client's data is represented as a separate unit within the federated dataset. 4.11 shows how federated data would look for a dataset comprising 5 clients.¹

```
Client dataset for LCLid MAC000226
OrderedDict([('x', <tf.Tensor: shape=(17191, 336), dtype=float32, numpy=
array([[0.076, 0.132, 0.176, ..., 0.247, 0.261, 0.241],
       [0.132, 0.176, 0.24, ..., 0.261, 0.241, 0.701],
       [0.176, 0.24, 0.098, ..., 0.241, 0.701, 0.238],
       ...,
       [0.674, 0.173, 0.08, ..., 0.321, 0.311, 0.302],
       [0.173, 0.08, 0.081, ..., 0.311, 0.302, 0.287],
       [0.08, 0.081, 0.063, ..., 0.302, 0.287, 0.222]], dtype=float32>)], ('y', <tf.Tensor: shape=(17191, 1), dtype=float32, numpy=
array([[0.701],
       [0.238],
       [0.22 ],
       ...,
       [0.287],
       [0.222],
       [0.177]], dtype=float32)>)])
```

Fig. 4.10 Ordered Dictionary Converted Data for a Random Client

```
Number of client datasets: 22
First dataset: < PrefetchDataset element_spec=OrderedDict([('x', TensorSpec(shape=(None, 336), dtype=tf.float32, name=None)), ('y', TensorSpec(shape=(None, 1), dtype=tf.float32, name=None))])>
Second dataset: < PrefetchDataset element_spec=OrderedDict([('x', TensorSpec(shape=(None, 336), dtype=tf.float32, name=None)), ('y', TensorSpec(shape=(None, 1), dtype=tf.float32, name=None))])>
Third dataset: < PrefetchDataset element_spec=OrderedDict([('x', TensorSpec(shape=(None, 336), dtype=tf.float32, name=None)), ('y', TensorSpec(shape=(None, 1), dtype=tf.float32, name=None))])>
Fourth dataset: < PrefetchDataset element_spec=OrderedDict([('x', TensorSpec(shape=(None, 336), dtype=tf.float32, name=None)), ('y', TensorSpec(shape=(None, 1), dtype=tf.float32, name=None))])>
Fifth dataset: < PrefetchDataset element_spec=OrderedDict([('x', TensorSpec(shape=(None, 336), dtype=tf.float32, name=None)), ('y', TensorSpec(shape=(None, 1), dtype=tf.float32, name=None))])>
```

Fig. 4.11 Federated Data Instance of random 5 clients

4.5 Model, Hyper-parameter, and Optimizers

To address the objective of deploying a small neural network at the edge, we have designed a simple 4-layer (2 input, 1 hidden, 1 output) sequential neural network 4.12. The first layer of the neural network takes the input shape, which depends on the window size used during the sliding window approach. In this layer, there are 16 units connected to the input. The second layer consists of 8 units, which receive the output from the previous layer as input. The third layer has 4 units and the final layer has a single unit for value prediction. Throughout the network, the rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function is utilized, with RMSE, MAE, and MSE considered for loss functions and metrics. The learning rate for local clients is kept at 0.01.

¹For Detailed Code, refer to GitHub page: <https://github.com/ADG4050/Federated-Learning-Approach-towards-Smart-Energy-Meter-Dataset>

By employing this compact neural network architecture, we aim to achieve efficient edge training without overwhelming computational demands. The simplicity of the model allows for faster training and deployment while still capturing the essential patterns and trends in the data.

Fig. 4.12 Local Client Model Structure

The global model performs a mean aggregation of the local model parameters contributed by each client. The global model learning rate, which determines the step size for updating the global model parameters during aggregation, is set to 1.0 by default. The below image depicts 4.13, how a global model weights parameters look like, before aggregation and after aggregation. The Global model weights and the finalizers in the image depict how the global server expects and receives the model representation from the clients.

A basic unit test checker function was implemented to verify the functionality of the TFF built-in function (`tff.federatedmean()`) 4.14 for mean aggregation at the global level. The function aimed to confirm whether the mean aggregation accurately calculates

```
( -> <
  global_model_weights=<
    trainable=<
      float32[336,16],
      float32[16],
      float32[16,8],
      float32[8],
      float32[8,4],
      float32[4],
      float32[4,1],
      float32[1]
    >,
    non_trainable=<>
  >,
  distributor=<>,
  client_work=<>,
  aggregator=<
    value_sum_process=<>,
    weight_sum_process=<>
  >,
  finalizer=<
    int64,
    float32[336,16],
    float32[16],
    float32[16,8],
    ...
    float32[4,1],
    float32[1]
  >
>@SERVER)
```

Fig. 4.13 Global Model Initialisation

the aggregated mean value. The image 4.14 provided serves as a confirmation of the functionality of global aggregation. Five random inputs were passed through the mean aggregation function, and the resulting aggregated mean value was obtained.

```
@tff.federated_computation(tff.FederatedType(tf.float32, tff.CLIENTS))
def unit_test_global_average(client_values):
    return tff.federated_mean(client_values)

unit_test_global_average([68.5, 70.3, 69.8, 56.2])
✓ 0.0s
66.200005
```

Fig. 4.14 Global Model Aggregation Checker Function

4.6 Non-i.i.d Pattern Exhibition

To account for the non-i.i.d. connection issues between edge devices in federated training, our simulation incorporates a randomization algorithm. This algorithm ensures that in each federated round, a subset of 15 random clients is only selected to form the federated dataset used for training. This approach allows our simulation to emulate the challenges and complexities of training models in a federated setting, where non-i.i.d. connections between edge devices can impact the learning process.

4.7 TFF - Computations

In TFF Computations, we describe the whole training procedure available in the TFF framework. The whole process revolves around two main functions, the "initialize" function and the "next" function.

The "initialize" function is responsible for initializing the global model by obtaining the initial trainable variables from the server. This step is typically performed at the beginning of the federated learning process to ensure that all clients start with the same initial model parameters before training begins.

The "next" function plays a crucial role in the federated learning process. It initiates a new round of training and federated averaging by broadcasting the current server weights to all the clients. Each client then updates its individual model using the received server

weights and sends back the updated model to the server. The server collects these client updates and performs an aggregation step to create a new global model. Each time the next functionality is executed, it represents a new round of training and federated averaging being executed.²

For our case, the next functionality is performed 15 times, with a random 15 different clients federated dataset selected every time, so that the overall global level model loss converges.

²For Detailed Code, refer to GitHub page: <https://github.com/ADG4050/Federated-Learning-Approach-towards-Smart-Energy-Meter-Dataset>

CHAPTER 5

Results and Analysis

5.1 Federated Training Analysis

As explained before, the data is divided based on two training scenarios. For daily, weekly, and monthly prediction, the model is trained on both 2012 year and 2013 year data and tested on two months of 2014. For the year-wide prediction, the data is trained on only 2012 year data, and tested on the total 2013 data.

Regarding Federated Learning (FL), the convergence of training loss is achieved by completing a certain number of Federated rounds until convergence is reached. To simulate real-life non-i.i.d. (independent and identically distributed) device behavior, a fraction of the total available clients are randomly selected for each Federated round using a randomizing algorithm within each cluster. This approach ensures that the data is representative of real-world scenarios and captures the diversity of devices participating in the Federated Learning process.

Additionally, for this simulation only, it is important to note that the selection of available clients in the simulation is influenced by the computational limitations of the platform used, specifically Google Colab. The number of clients chosen for each round is adjusted to align with the capabilities of the Colab environment, ensuring that the simulation remains feasible within the given constraints.

5.1.1 Confirmation of Model Hyper-parameters

The confirmation of hyper-parameters refers to the process of determining the optimal learning rate and batch size for the client-side model. In this case, the Cluster-07 data and model are utilized, and the results obtained are extrapolated to the other Cluster Models. To conduct the simulation for hyperparameter selection, a random subset of 15 clients is chosen for each federated round from the pool of available clients within the cluster and the loss (RMSE) and (MAE) is observed across 15 rounds 5.1.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5.1 Selection of Batch size and learning rate for the client side model based on global loss computed after 15 Federated rounds

- Keeping the Client side learning rate = 0.02, the global loss is computed 5.1a with batch sizes 24, Shuffle Buffer 120, Prefetch Buffer 12, and in the next scenario with batch size 12, shuffle Buffer 60, Prefetch Buffer 6.
- With the batch size fixed at 12, the global loss is computed 5.1b for client-side learning rates 0.02 and 0.01.
- Based on our findings with a batch size of 12 and a learning rate of 0.01, lower values of MAE were observed. This outcome supports our recommendation to proceed with training using these specific hyperparameters. It wouldn't be practical to choose an even smaller batch size or learning rate as it would significantly increase the computational time required to reach the global minimum.

5.1.2 Training Loss across different Clusters

After fixing the learning rate and batch size, the training loss is computed for multiple rounds across different clusters until convergence is achieved. In order to provide a demonstration, six clusters are selected based on their average consumption levels.

First, clusters 8 and 9 (5.2a) are chosen as low-average consumption clusters. These clusters likely represent devices or entities with relatively low energy consumption patterns. Overall, at an average 20 federated rounds are required for this training data to get converged. In our context, convergence is considered to be achieved when there are only changes in the loss values that are visible up to the fourth decimal floating point. This means that the optimization process continues until the loss values reach a stable state where further iterations result in minimal changes in the loss function, typically within the fourth decimal place. It is observed, 5.2a that for Cluster - 08, a better training loss (MAE) is obtained, which means less in our context, compared to Cluster - 09.

For, clusters 14 and 4 which are medium average consumption clusters, similarly, as before, 20 federated rounds 5.2b are enough for the loss to get converged. The loss obtained is a little bit higher than the low-consumption clusters because the average consumption of these clusters is a little bit higher than the previous ones.

Finally, clusters 7 and 18 are identified as high-average consumption clusters. These clusters likely exhibit higher energy consumption patterns compared to the other selected clusters. Despite Cluster - 18, having the highest mean consumption, its loss gets converged better than Cluster 7 (5.2c).

Since MAE does not reflect the correct performance metrics alone, the below table 5.1 shows the final MAPE values obtained at the final federated rounds of training for these 6 clusters together with MAE. However, for checking the loss convergence MAE can be used

(a) Training Loss Cluster 08 and 09

(b) Training Loss Cluster 04 and 14

(c) Training Loss Cluster 07 and 18

Fig. 5.2 Training Convergence Graphs across Different Clusters

as a standalone metric. On average 21.7 percent is the training error obtained across all Clusters, which looks reasonable.

Table 5.1 Federated Training Results Across 6 Clusters

Cluster	Federated Rounds	MAE	MAPE
8	20	0.0535	23.24%
9	20	0.0553	29.12%
4	20	0.0906	23.23%
14	20	0.1432	28.64%
7	20	0.2007	22.80%
18	20	0.1953	16.88%

5.2 Federated Evaluation

For our evaluation, we proceeded cluster-wise by selecting three clusters. Each cluster contains a confined level of average consumption: one with high average consumption (Cluster - 18), one with moderate average consumption (Cluster - 04), and one with low average consumption (Cluster - 08). For each cluster, we examined the monthly, weekly, and daily prediction errors for different types of households to assess our complete algorithm.

5.2.1 Detailed Evaluation - Cluster 08, 04 and 18

Monthly Load Forecast with short-term prediction

For the monthly forecast, we trained the data on the year 2012 and made predictions for the entire year of 2013. Ideally, we selected two types of households: one that received all the global model updates and one that didn't receive some of the global updates during training. This differentiation aimed to highlight the non-i.i.d. (non-independent and identically distributed) issue.

Furthermore, the selected households that did not receive some of the updates, were further divided into inter-cluster examples. These examples included a high consumption example, a moderate consumption example, and a low consumption example). With these, now evaluation is performed on the high bounds and the low bounds of the possible local models in the cluster.

Table 5.2 Monthly Load Forecasting RMSE - Comparison between different Households - Cluster 08

Month	Client Type (RMSE)			
	Moderate (All)	Moderate (Non-i.i.d)	High (Non-i.i.d)	Low (Non-i.i.d)
January	0.0636	0.1465	0.2507	0.0778
February	0.0633	0.1213	0.2581	0.0665
March	0.0623	0.2346	0.2875	0.0760
April	0.0544	0.1320	0.1531	0.0797
May	0.0570	0.1612	0.0866	0.0740
June	0.0621	0.1316	0.0583	0.0752
July	0.0638	0.1329	0.1690	0.7425
August	0.0662	0.1345	0.2217	0.7119
September	0.0528	0.0866	0.1417	0.0730
October	0.0611	0.1222	0.1896	0.0695
November	0.0539	0.1383	0.2505	0.0684
December	0.0650	0.1357	0.2484	0.0787

Table 5.2 presents the RMSE (Root Mean Square Error) values for all the types of households described above. Overall, we observe better prediction for households that received all the updates in comparison to those that missed out on some or all of the updates.

Similarly, we performed the same evaluation for Cluster-04. However, for this cluster, we analyzed the performance of clients who received all the global updates in a more detailed way, dividing it into 3 categories (see Table 5.3), which had high, low, and moderate consumption households of the cluster. The final column of the table is for a moderate consumption household that did not receive all the global updates.

Compared to Cluster-08, we observed similar RMSE values for moderate consumption households that received all updates and households that did not receive some of them. This leads to the conclusion that this cluster likely has most households with local models that are closer to the global model.

For Cluster 18, we analyzed the RMSE in a slightly different way. We selected two households that received all global updates and two households with non-i.i.d. updates. The results are shown in Table 5.4.

From the table, it can be observed that the average RMSE between the two selected households that received all updates is 0.35. On the other hand, the average RMSE for households that did not receive all updates is 0.42. This suggests that households in

Table 5.3 Monthly Load Forecasting RMSE - Comparison between different Households - Cluster 04

Month	Client Type (RMSE)			
	Moderate (All)	High (All)	Low (All)	Moderate (Non-i.i.d)
January	0.1839	0.2073	0.1364	0.1512
February	0.1894	0.2114	0.1496	0.1403
March	0.1762	0.2123	0.1779	0.2300
April	0.1766	0.1771	0.1530	0.1860
May	0.1802	0.1902	0.1430	0.1450
June	0.1606	0.1563	0.1366	0.1004
July	0.1430	0.1758	0.1090	0.1311
August	0.1772	0.1920	0.1344	0.1217
September	0.1705	0.2027	0.1300	0.1515
October	0.1574	0.1978	0.1483	0.1426
November	0.1771	0.2036	0.1481	0.1768
December	0.2034	0.2165	0.1695	0.1342

Cluster - 18 that received all updates tend to have slightly lower RMSE values compared to households that did not receive all updates. The difference in RMSE values could be attributed to the impact of global updates on improving the accuracy of local models in certain cases.

Table 5.4 Monthly Load Forecasting RMSE - Comparison between different Households - Cluster 18

Month	Client Type (RMSE)			
	Moderate (All)	High (All)	Moderate (Non-i.i.d)	High (Non-i.i.d)
January	0.3454	0.4012	0.3843	0.7139
February	0.3638	0.2843	0.3833	0.7333
March	0.3311	0.3604	0.5887	0.2769
April	0.3400	0.2998	0.4700	0.2600
May	0.3612	0.2950	0.4467	0.2040
June	0.5078	0.2677	0.3242	0.1981
July	0.5822	0.3106	0.2715	0.2008
August	0.4927	0.2700	0.2477	0.1933
September	0.4034	0.2700	0.3371	0.5429
October	0.3970	0.2626	0.3404	0.6637
November	0.3827	0.2880	0.4619	0.7876
December	0.3551	0.3193	0.4515	0.7373

Weekly Load Forecast 5.3 with short term prediction

Starting with cluster 08, for the weekly forecast, we selected two random weeks: one from January and one from September, as shown in Figure 5.3a and 5.3b. This choice was made to observe different seasonal week prediction traits. On average, similar RMSE losses were predicted for both weeks when tested in a household that did not receive some of the global model updates. The noticeable trend observed is that, for both weeks, the average RMSE is around 0.05 for weekends and 0.16 for weekdays.

For Cluster 04, similarly, we chose two random weeks from March and November and obtained average RMSE values as shown in Figure 5.3c and 5.3d. The average RMSE for March was around 0.129, and for November, it was around 0.089. Interestingly, for the tested week in March, the RMSE remains the same over both weekends and weekdays. However, in the case of November, it follows the trend observed in Cluster-08, with lower RMSE values on weekends compared to weekdays.

And finally, for Cluster 18, we picked two random weeks, one belonging to the month of May and the other one from February. We observed that the RMSE remains higher for weekdays compared to weekends. However, for the month of February 5.3f, we observed a separate pattern. The RMSE values were quite even across both weekdays and weekends, suggesting that the predictions were more consistent between these days during that particular month.

Stress Test - Short Term Prediction in Festive Days across Clusters

For the short-term prediction accuracy of our model, we assess its performance across a three-day span: 24th Dec, 25th Dec, and 26th Dec, encompassing 6 clusters. We plot the actual versus predicted values per half-hourly interval. These selected 6 clusters' results can be extrapolated and used for other clusters as well, as they cover all kinds of bounds based on the historical data analysis. Furthermore, the selected days include festival days, which act as a stress performance test for our model's accuracy. These festive occasions often exhibit unique consumption patterns, making them crucial for evaluating our model's robustness under challenging and diverse scenarios.

The graph below 5.4 shows that despite having to forecast during a festive day span when unusual consumption activities can occur—such as households being empty or extra full, or extra machinery being used—almost all of the peaks are accurately predicted. This is remarkable considering the short half-hourly prediction duration. It confirms that all the local models of households from various clusters are well-trained enough to make accurate predictions even for very short time spans.

Fig. 5.3 Moderate Consumption Household weekly RMSE across cluster - 08, 04, and 18

Actual vs. Predicted Values - Short Term Daily Forecasting (Cluster 08 Moderate Consumption Household)

(a) Cluster 08

Actual vs. Predicted Values - Short Term Daily Forecasting (Cluster 04 Moderate Consumption Household)

(b) Cluster 04

Actual vs. Predicted Values - Short Term Daily Forecasting (Cluster 18 Moderate Consumption Household)

(c) Cluster 18

Actual vs. Predicted Values - Short Term Daily Forecasting (Cluster 07 Moderate Consumption Household)

(d) Cluster 07

Actual vs. Predicted Values - Short Term Daily Forecasting (Cluster 09 Moderate Consumption Household)

(e) Cluster 09

Fig. 5.4 Short Term Daily Forecasting (24th Dec - 26th Dec) across Clusters

Finally, a few of the peaks that are not accurately predicted could be attributed to sudden uneven consumer behavior, which is a common trend observed during festive times. With most of the unaccounted peaks, the predictions being on the higher side rather than the lower side, it is safe to say that this proposed prediction algorithm is reliable enough to be put to use even in stress or most uneven periods.

Cluster Performance - Overall Summary

To summarize the performance of all three clusters together, we created box plots (see Figure 5.5) representing the monthly RMSE data across the entire year of prediction. We compared the households that received all updates to those that did not receive all the updates in different clusters.

In Cluster - 18, we observed the largest spread of RMSE values, indicating a notable difference between the minimum and maximum monthly RMSE values. This suggests that the predictive performance varies significantly among households in this cluster, with some achieving relatively accurate results while others experience higher prediction errors.

On the other hand, Cluster-08 showed the most outlier points, which are data points outside the box plot range when averaged. This indicates that there are more instances of extreme RMSE values in Cluster - 08 compared to Cluster - 18 and suggests a greater variation in predictive accuracy among households in this cluster. Overall, the analysis of the box plots highlights the variations in predictive performance among the clusters and households based on the updates they received.

In Table 5.5, we have summarized all our findings regarding the prediction accuracy for different scenarios in the three clusters. The table includes the RMSE and MAPE values for each scenario.

- Normal Scenario refers to households that received all global updates.
- Worst Case Scenario refers to households that have not received any updates and have household average consumption significantly different from the cluster average.

Based on our analysis, **the average monthly RMSE across the three clusters, representing lower, moderate, and upper average consumption levels, is 0.17**, with the best scenario as 0.06. **Similarly, the average monthly MAPE stands at 22.01**, with the best scenario as 16. In the worst-case scenario, **the average monthly RMSE is around 0.28, and the average monthly MAPE is 35.13**.

(a) Box Plots of monthly forecast - Cluster 08

(b) Box Plots of monthly forecast - Cluster 04

(c) Box Plots of monthly forecast - Cluster 18

Fig. 5.5 Box Plots of Monthly Forecasts for Different Clusters

These metrics provide an overall picture of the prediction accuracy for the different scenarios and indicate the level of accuracy achieved in forecasting energy consumption for households within each cluster.

Table 5.5 Analysing Performance for Different Clusters and Scenarios

Clusters	Aggregation	Normal Scenario			Worst Case Scenario		
		MAE	RMSE	MAPE	MAE	RMSE	MAPE
8	Average - Monthly	0.0377	0.0604	23.26%	0.1449	0.1929	46.75%
4	Average - Monthly	0.0854	0.1509	26.68%	0.1153	0.1953	31.58%
18	Average - Monthly	0.2052	0.3024	16.09%	0.4203	0.4593	27.06%

5.3 Performance comparison against a Centralized Learning Model

For comparison against a centralized environment, we established the following conditions. Firstly, we set up a centralized server model where all data is sent to the central server. To maintain a fair comparison, we kept the participation ratio three times higher than the Federated setup, based on the computational resources we possess, keeping in mind the fact that centralized training does not have a non-i.i.d scenario.

Both the Federated and centralized setups were evaluated with 20 rounds of training for the Federated setup and 20 epochs of training for the centralized setup.

The bar graphs below 5.6 show the monthly prediction RMSE values across the three clusters. While for Cluster - 08 and 04, we observe a better RMSE cluster average for the Federated setup, for Cluster 18, the centralized setup has a better RMSE. On average, across the three clusters, we can see that both the Federated and Centralized setups have an average RMSE of around 0.1712 and 0.1799 respectively. **Achieving a similar level of accuracy as a centralized model was one of the objectives of this thesis, and these results demonstrate that we have accomplished it.**

The table presented 5.6 below showcases the monthly statistics across the mentioned clusters (Cluster-08, Cluster-04, and Cluster-18) for both the Federated and centralized environments. These RMSE metrics are essential for evaluating the accuracy of the predictive models used in the clusters. Overall, the findings demonstrate that the Federated approach achieves competitive performance, closely resembling the accuracy achieved by the Centralized model, which aligns with the key objective of this thesis.

Fig. 5.6 Bar Graph Comparison of Centralized vs Federated Setup

Table 5.6 RMSE Results in Federated and Centralized Setup for Different Clusters

Cluster	Setup	Mean RMSE	Max RMSE	Min RMSE	Std. Dev. RMSE
08	Federated	0.0605	0.0662	0.0528	0.0045
08	Centralized	0.0663	0.0868	0.0557	0.0082
04	Federated	0.1509	0.2300	0.1004	0.0322
04	Centralized	0.1952	0.2152	0.1570	0.0161
18	Federated	0.3024	0.4012	0.2626	0.0398
18	Centralized	0.2772	0.3306	0.2505	0.0219

5.3.1 Communication Cost Comparison

For a Federated setup, we compute the total communication cost as twice as the number of federated training rounds multiplied by the model size shared and the number of active participants, but for a centralized setup, it is the whole year's data of each client multiplied by the number of clients and the total number of epochs. The whole year data of a client is around 0.65 Mb, whereas the model size for a federated setup is 0.0212 Mb. On average, for federated setup, we have 15 active clients and for centralized setup, it is considered 45.

Having all the values, when computed we get the **communication cost for 15 active participants in federated setup as 12.72 Mb**, whereas **for centralized setup with overall 45 participants, the communication cost will be 585 Mb**. Even if 15 participants are considered like a federated setup, it will be 195 Mb. In conclusion, with a complete year of data being almost 23 times as model size, the whole communication cost for a federated setup is much less than a centralized setup.

Based on the above formulation it can be said that for federated learning to have less communication cost than centralized setup, the model size should be less than half of the client dataset size. However the smaller the size of the selected model, the lesser the communication overhead is.

5.4 Performance comparison against similar recent works

When comparing our load forecasting model with the federated architecture used in Savi's work [37], we focused on the average Monthly RMSE values across three clusters, each consisting of maximum, minimum, and moderate consumption households. It is important to note that **the number of participating clients in our work, (the equivalent term in M.Savi's work is the number of nodes) considered, was 42, while Savi's simulation, involved 80 nodes.**

While an increase in nodes does not guarantee performance improvement, it might lead to a better global model depending on the consumption profile of the newly considered nodes. Another crucial factor in this comparison is the complexity of the models used. Savi's work deployed LSTM, whereas our simulation was based on simple sequential networks. **The number of parameters required for Savi's simulation was 7505, while our proposed setup only required 5569 parameters, which reduces the communication cost.**

Table 5.7 Comparison of RMSE between Our Proposed Model and M. Savi Model

Month	Our Proposed Model (RMSE)	M. Savi Model (RMSE)
January	0.2053	0.1463
February	0.1626	0.153
March	0.2176	0.1535
April	0.1800	0.1345
May	0.1657	0.1304
June	0.1434	0.1259
July	0.1685	0.1057
August	0.1526	0.1106
September	0.1581	0.1302
October	0.1554	0.1335
November	0.1729	0.1471
December	0.1728	0.1328

The table above (Table 5.7) illustrates that despite having 50 percent fewer nodes and 20 percent fewer computational requirements for the local model, we achieved similar levels of RMSE. On average, our cluster RMSE was 0.17, whereas, in M. Savi’s work, it was 0.14. While, again RMSE alone doesn’t justify the prediction performance, clubbing it together with MAPE (which is not considered in M.Savi’s work) would provide a better scope of comparison. However, this finding demonstrates that we achieved almost equal predictive performance despite using fewer devices and computational resources [37].

For a fairer comparison, we assess Taik’s work [40], which involves a participation ratio of 36 percent, compared to only 10 percent in our proposed approach. Although Taik’s model also utilizes LSTM and personalized local model improvement rounds, our combined approach of clustering and sequential models yields superior results. It is worth noting that Taik’s work is based on only 5 federated rounds, while our approach involves 20 federated rounds. However, upon reviewing our model training graphs, we observed that the difference in Mean Absolute Error (MAE) between 5 federated rounds and 20 federated rounds is merely 0.005. When this difference is measured against the cluster average, it accounts for only a 4 percent change in performance. Considering this slight deviation, we can confidently assert that our proposed model outperforms Taik’s approach. The performance comparison is presented in Table 5.8.

Table 5.8 Comparison of Participation Ratio, Number of Rounds, and Average MAPE

Model	Participation Ratio	No of Rounds	Avg MAPE
Taik's Model	36%	5	34.14%
Our Proposed Model	10.50%	20	22.01%

5.5 Energy Overhead of the Proposed Model: Simulating the DNN Model in a Resource Constraint Environment

By energy overhead, we refer to the amount of energy required by a smart device to execute our proposed model. To calculate this overhead, we conducted a simulation on an Arduino UNO R4 Wifi, using the UART connection, which features an 8-bit processor, representing one of the most challenging resource-constrained situations for our model. For the simulation, we used a TFT USB Tester to measure energy consumption.

The simulation involved running our model for Model Training on a day's data in the Arduino UNO and predicting the next day's data in it. For each measured half-hour predicted reading observed, through the UNO serial Monitor, which would we maintained a 10-second buffer, emulating the half-hour process. A Sample output 5.8 obtained from the UNO's serial Monitor is shown below for reference. For the energy measurement, we started by measuring the mWh (milliwatt-hours) consumed without the model running, and then we measured the mWh again with the model running.

Fig. 5.7 Energy Consumption Readings in Arduino UNO


```
Output Serial Monitor x
Message (Enter to send message to 'Arduino UNO R4 WIFI' on 'COM3')
16:41:25.908 -> Half Hourly Prediction 14: 1.75
16:41:36.377 -> Half Hourly Prediction 15: 5.72
16:41:46.862 -> Half Hourly Prediction 16: 6.52
16:41:57.349 -> Half Hourly Prediction 17: 7.39
16:42:07.815 -> Half Hourly Prediction 18: 7.47
16:42:18.301 -> Half Hourly Prediction 19: 3.14
16:42:28.773 -> Half Hourly Prediction 20: 3.66
16:42:39.229 -> Half Hourly Prediction 21: 2.55
16:42:49.751 -> Half Hourly Prediction 22: 2.91
16:43:00.237 -> Half Hourly Prediction 23: 4.25
16:43:10.712 -> Half Hourly Prediction 24: 4.16
16:43:21.182 -> Half Hourly Prediction 25: 4.09
16:43:31.677 -> Half Hourly Prediction 26: 3.86
16:43:42.143 -> Half Hourly Prediction 27: 3.29
```

Fig. 5.8 Arduino UNO Serial Monitor Output (Emulating a Prediction Model)

From the above images, the first image 5.7a depicts the initial readings with everything at zero, suggesting the device being unbiased, the second image 5.7b shows a half-hour measured mWh reading - 220, and the third image 5.7c shows a half-hour measured mWh reading - 245. Extrapolating it to an hour, there is a difference of 50 mWh between the two readings. **This indicates that our model will consume approximately only an additional 50 mWh on top of the real smart meter default consumption, which is a negligible amount and can be incorporated without any noticeable impact.**

CHAPTER 6

Conclusions

Based on the above results, we can confidently conclude that the objectives laid out before starting this thesis have been successfully achieved. These objectives included creating a federated framework for load forecasting, achieving prediction metrics comparable to the state-of-the-art while utilizing fewer computational resources, and simulating real-world federated learning scenarios, particularly those related to non-i.i.d. issues. To tackle all these scenarios, we have introduced various novel approaches, such as incorporating clustering techniques prior to federated learning application to have an optimal global model and implementing a randomized client selection algorithm to emulate non-i.i.d. scenarios.

Based on the extensive analysis presented in Chapter 5, it is evident that deploying a simple sequential neural network as the client model within the federated learning framework yields highly accurate load predictions, with an average MAPE of only 22 percent. This demonstrates the effectiveness of our approach in load forecasting.

Furthermore, our results show that despite utilizing fewer computational resources and client participation compared to other computationally exhaustive models, our simple sequential neural networks can achieve prediction performance that is nearly as good. This finding highlights the efficiency and practicality of our approach, as it provides accurate load predictions while minimizing computational requirements and client involvement.

CHAPTER 7

Ethical Considerations and Future Works

7.1 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are vital when taking research into consideration as the complete ethical process takes care of whether any human or living subject is harmed in the process, whether the data (personal or not) are stored properly, whether the research abides the GDPR laws, and regulations, which all, in the end, defines the quality of the research.

While Federated learning is itself a privacy mechanism learning, designed keeping ethical considerations in mind, any simulation done for researching this framework, might deal with crucial real historical data. Special care should be taken to keep such crucial data hidden. Data involving people's livelihoods should be dealt with extra care, with the concerned being fully informed about the purpose and requirements of the study. This makes sure that everyone involved is fully aware of any risk that may be associated with the research, whilst making them assured of the potential benefits of the work.

7.2 Future Works

Moreover, since Federated Learning operates within a framework where only model updates are shared, there have been a few research studies addressing the concern of data identification based on model update trends. Nasr et al. (2019) ([41] and Zhu et al. (2019) [42] have demonstrated that it is possible to infer whether a specific data sample belongs

to a particular dataset by analyzing the model gradient patterns. To address this issue, one potential solution is to explore and test the combination of Differential Privacy setup with Federated Learning for load forecasting. This approach could potentially enhance the privacy protection of individual data samples during the collaborative learning process.

Additionally, the use of IOT-integrated smart meters, where based on the output of FL, the meters decide when to turn on the home apparatus, is also a research area that could be explored.

And finally, taking this approach to further grid-level load forecasting from lower-level substations to higher-level substations aggregating the results of clusters in lower-level substations obtained from individual households focusing on mid-term or long-term forecasting, could also be looked upon.

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